

An Examination of the Intersection of Religion with Politics in Nigeria

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Abstract

The interplay between religion and politics in Nigeria is an enormous and explosive one. It is explosive because religion has remained a major factor determining political power and social identity since politics is all about struggle for power and any attempt by anyone, be it opposition parties, individual or groups which threatened their interest were fought using religion as political weaponry. Thus, this paper accessed the negative impact of religion on politics in Nigeria as a democratic nation. The study adopted historical and analytical approach, investigating the havoc the intersection of religion had caused politics in Nigeria. The paper ultimately argues that the influence of religion on politics has affected government plans, decision making and policies leading to the fact that the intersection of religion with politics had led to the extermination of good governance, using religion and ethnicity as bait for voting, and has further polarized and got the nation divided into camps among others. This paper recommends that it is high time we dissected and expunged the intersection of religion with politics and concludes that autochthonous constitution should be given where secularity in the true sense of it should be promoted.

Keywords: Politics, Religion, Nigeria Intersection, Political Parties.

Introduction

The intersection of religion with politics in Nigeria is no doubt as old as partisan politics itself. It is germane to note that ever before independence religion has had its grips on politics in Nigeria. Therefore, the interplay between religion and politics is an enormous and explosive one. It is explosive because religion has remained a major factor determining political power and social identity. Buttressing this fact, Gwamna observes that today, religion has become a major defining factor of identity in Nigeria.¹ Adding to this, Danmole opines that in the struggle for political power, various variables ranging from ethnic solidarity to religion were used by the politicians to canvass for support.²

It is therefore pertinent to indicate here, that the Intersection of religion in Nigeria politics has led to prejudices which has created avenue for opportunist to use these differences as a means of political bargaining and differentiation. This political persuasion and differences has been located in religion for as Matthew Kukah rightly observes that: “To date, many would argue that Nigeria politics has essentially been how to wrest power... And equitably distribute it around Nigeria. Whatever may be the weakness or otherwise of this argument, it offers trajectory within which to examine the role and place of religion in national politics in Nigeria.”³

Since politics is associated with interest, state, authority, consent and power and how to distribute power equitably, the corresponding effect is using religion and other sentiments to get attention. All political parties formed in Nigeria during the first political dispensation such as the Northern People Congress (NPC) the Action Group (AG), the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC), Northern Element Progressive Union (NEPU) even, the second Republic Parties, National Party of Nigeria (NPN), Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN), and Peoples Redemption Party and others all had religious colouration, while at the establishment of Peoples Democratic Party (PDP), All Nigerian Peoples Party (ANPP), Action Congress of Nigeria (ACN) that

metamorphosed to All Progressive Congress (APC) and other parties had religious affiliations which portend danger for Nigeria democracy.

It is the opinion of the authors of this paper that religion has played destructive roles in Nigerian politics. The words of Gaya Best is instructive here, when he notes that “Religion is becoming a divisive issue and constitute a growing conflict flash point.⁴ Therefore, it is the intention of this paper to examine the intersection of religion in Nigeria politics and also looks into the implication of the intersection of religion in politics, recommendation, then, conclusion.

The Concepts of Religion and Politics

In the work of this nature, the basic term must be explained. Although religion and politics are common place concepts, it does not mean that their respective connotations are always clearly and commonly shared.⁵ We define what is religion?

Religion

Religion in particular is an elusive concept which means different things to different people. It has been observed by some scholars that religion has no consensus meaning. To many religion is a way of life, and to some, is the way that people serve their maker. While others sees it as a way of worshipping God. Emile Durkheim defines religion as that which deals with the sacred things set apart and forbidden.⁶ Put differently, religion has been defined as system of belief, ritual and practices a code of moral conduct involving the recognition by man of a superhuman power which has control over his destiny and which is entitled to obedience, reference and worship.⁷ In order not to be drawn into the rather definitional maze, we take as our working definition King’s definition of religion as cited by Isiramen which aptly describes religion, as derived from three Latin words namely; *Religare* (to unite or link), *Ligare* (to bind) and *Religio* (Relationship).⁸ Defining religion in this way has stressed the negative aspect of religion because of the havoc it has caused politics in Nigeria. Aderibigbe in his observation says that if religion is seen as a factor that binds it may depict a followership that becomes unreasonably fanatical as a result of being wedged together by rules, obligations and responsibilities that are dogmatically essential to the laws and observance of their religion.⁹

The above observed views suits our discussion not because religion is part of man kind but because it portrays adherents that becomes unreasonably fanatical as a result of being wedged together by the essentials and observance of their religion. It is to be observed that since religion is seen as a factor that binds people together, it is rather easy for those in the same religion to use it as a form of persuasion and negotiation upon joining political parties, which has been the order of the day in Nigeria.

Politics

Politics, no doubt, is also complex and difficult to define. According to Illustrated Oxford Dictionary, politics is the art and science of government.¹⁰ In other words, Awolowo defines politics as the science and art of the management of public affairs.¹¹ Onyekpe in his view sees politics as the struggle for power which in itself is the authority to determine or formulate and execute decision and policies which must be accepted. Again, it is a struggle for power of governance, especially executive authority.¹² From the above, it is to be noted that politics is all about struggle for power as it relates to the management and control of such power in governance. Thus, politics involves how a state is governed and how political leaders get their mandate. Since it is a process, most of the political office holders in Nigeria used religion as a yardstick of getting land slide victory over others. Therefore, the question that serves as a poser is, has religion intersected politics in Nigeria? The answer is yes, because right from the inception of partisan politics in Nigeria religion had been a defining factor, determining political power and social identity. Religion no doubt has a great influence in Nigeria politics. Having attempts the literal and technical meaning of “Religion” and “Politics”, the discussion to follow focuses on the influence of Religion on the Nigerian politics.

The Influence of Religion on Politics in Nigeria

When religion and politics are discussed, one wonders as to whether the two subjects are mutually exclusive or unconnected. On this note, Chilufa observes that academically the two are treated as independent and existent in their own individual right. In practical sense, their relation are equally vague.¹³ As a result of the vaguely relationship between religion and politics, this led Umeanolue to reiterates that, the obvious interplay between religion and politics has attracted the reactions of scholars and what seems the consensus of such reactions is the ambivalent role of religion in the growth, development and survival of Nigerian nation.¹⁴ Again, he said it is not a small question to ask in which way religion involves itself in political realm for on this depend to some measure how much value Nigeria attached to their faith.¹⁵ This is to say that the influence of religion on Nigeria politics could be positive and negative. Here, in this paper we are stressing the negative impact of religion on politic in Nigeria, because it has not faired well in their act of politicking. In view of this, Ekwenife asserts that since religion and politics are too vital institutions of mankind, both of them interact and affect society at different level.¹⁶ Again, he goes further to notes that: "... here religion is often used to subserve political needs and aspiration of ruling class, who see in religion a means of preserving an order that places them at the apex."¹⁷

He however, notes further that the existence and activities of religious specialists in this type of society make it impossible for the political group to subjugate religion completely.¹⁸ That is why they make themselves relevant by giving support to some political candidates. Therefore, the influence of religion on politics in Nigeria cannot be over emphasized. It is an established fact that, Nigerian society since pre and post independence till date is strongly engrossed in religion. As it is, religion is ineluctable in the sense that "politics and religion are Siamese twins, therefore inseparable."¹⁹ Ottoh and Akintola note that: "In other words they are two side of the same coin in the sense that politics allows power to flow between the visible material world and invisible spiritual world. Despite the linkage between politics and religion, they are not identical and they cannot be no matter how they are manipulated."²⁰ This no doubt, has led to a situation where governance has been slow and ineffectual. Alamu in his view of how religion has been slow and ineffectual. Contends that Nigeria public sees religiosity mostly as "Nigercentric" affairs which influences policy making and decision taking.²¹ According to him this Niger-centricism describes the public and political dominance of religion in Nigeria, for he further posits that: "the geography of religion influenced the geography of politics in all national decisions, including elective and appointive offices even in conducting admission."²²

The above observation, is true in the sence that religion influence the features and arrangement in the ways things are done in politics at all national decisions and policy making. Corroborating the above view, the word of Dalandi is instructive here when he copiously elucidates that: "government action on religious matters shows that the nation's position of non interference into religious matters is not necessarily true. Practice and development in Nigeria history has shown marked differences with the theory as stated in the constitution."²³ It is therefore imperative to note that Nigeria is a secular state, making it a multi-religious state with the view that the government should stands aloof without interference in matters of religion but reverse is the case; one would agree to the fact that, all national issues are reduced to religion.

Firstly, it is imperative to note very strongly that the inculcation of Sharia into Nigeria constitution has shown how religion has influenced government plans and decision making in Nigeria. It is necessary to note that religion is a potent factor in Nigerian politics threatening her secularity.²⁴ Ngwa in his observation of the influence of religion on politics notes that the issue of Sharia took a political dimension with the setting of the constitution Drafting Committee (CDC) in 1976 as part of the efforts to return the country to civil rule.²⁵ He explains further that:

In the draft constitution, the Moslem member of the committee wanted to make a Sharia law part and parcel of the Nigerian constitution. When the constituent assembly began to debate on the proposed constitution, Sharia was prominent, as there were divergent views in respect of its adoption, or non adoption. Expectedly, many Muslim were in support while Christians were

antagonistic ... but the debate continued and a walk out was staged by Muslim members of the Assembly.²⁶

The above have shown the influence of religion on politics in Nigeria where there are opposing view as to the inclusion of Sharia into the constitution which almost brought the constituent assembly to stale mate. However, this did not end there, Dalandi stoutly explains that the question of secularism has reverberated in the national discourse since the adoption of the Shariah penal legal system in twelve northern state between 1999 and 2000.²⁷

Secondly, one of the ways in which religion has influenced governance is the establishment of pilgrimage board by Nigerian government at all levels, i.e. Federal, State and local levels to give supports to religious activities of both in Muslim and Christian control led states of the federation.²⁸ It is noteworthy to again note the word of Dalandi when he apodictically comments that: "For example at all level government sponsored all their citizens/indigenes to holy pilgrimages (Mecca and Rome) which is wholly a religious and private affairs. Government conveniently achieve this by the establishment of the national Hajj commission for the Muslims and the National Pilgrims Commission for the Christians."²⁹ The involvement of government in sponsoring pilgrimage programmes of both Moslem and Christian have shown the influence of religion in government programmes. This singular act has punctured the spirit of secularism in which the government is expected to maintain neutrality.

In the light of the above, one of the ways in which religion influenced government plans, decision and programmes in some cases was when government sponsored the building of worship centres. It is a known fact that the building of the national mosque and ecumenical centre in the national capital in Abuja was sorely initiated by the federal government using public fund.³⁰ Apart from this understanding it has become a notable culture for Christian and Moslem prayer to be part of government programmes at public functions organized by the government. In fact Umeanolue posits that at public gathering such as political rally and national gathering, it is either prayer are not offered at all or they are offered by leaders or functionaries of the recognized religions. He notes further that, if the opening prayer was said by a Muslims, the Christian will say the closing prayer and vice-versa. Further still, Christianity and Islam are adequately taken care of as work free day are observed during their festivals.³¹ From the above, it has revealed that religion is a dominant factor in Nigeria politics.

To this end, this trend has also gained ground in political campaigns and rally. Eleagu in his view of how political actors employed various techniques in winning elections in Nigeria reports that: "In politics there are rules, techniques plans etc employed by the actors to knock out their opponents. They may be legitimate, illegitimate, moral, immoral combination of these even absurd in some cases. These include pacification, diplomacy, coveting state media and other infrastructure, negotiations, numbers, war and threat of wars, religion among others."³² From the above understanding the most potent techniques employed by political actors during voting and campaigns in some cases are based on religious sentiment. Corroborating this fact, Umeanolue point out that religion has been used to either canvass support for a candidate or dissuade a candidate from voting for him or her.³³

In congruence with the above, in the wake of political independence in Nigeria various political parties sprang up. The Northern Peoples Congress which became a dominant party in Northern Nigeria. Also, in the Western region Egbe Omo Oduduwa, a Yoruba cultural organisation had metamorphosed into political party the Action Group of Nigeria while the National Council of Nigeria Citizen (NCNC) which was established in 1944 became more attractive in the Eastern region.³⁴ Religion also had it grips on these parties. At this juncture, it is of value to note that religion was another dimension introduced into politics in Nigeria for the three established political parties to consolidate their powers in their regions. In fact, since politics, as it is well known involves constant struggle for power. It is observable that during the electioneering campaign, the leadership of the Northern Peoples' Congress capitalized on religious sentiment to canvass for support. For example, Chief Obafemi Awolowo was castigated upon and was referred to as *Kaffir* who would not bother about the religion of Islam.³⁵

However, religious sentiment could also account for the failure of Action Group, particularly in the area where Muslims were the dominant majority. It is sine-qua-non to also point out that Awolowo supporters who were also Muslims made preparations for him to visit Lagos Central Mosque where special prayers were offered for him and his party. During the occasion it was reported that he made cash donation to the mosque.³⁶ In fact the Muslim supporters drummed their supports for him during his visit to the mosque, one of the song sung by Muslim supporters during his visits to the mosque was:

*Ni so ni mosalasi, ni so ni mosalasi,
Bi o kirun b'okirun ni so n' mosalasi
Awolowo baba Olayinka
ni no n' mosalasi*

Meaning:

*Let go to the mosque. Let's go to the mosque.
It does not matter whether you pray or not
Awolowo father of Olayinka
Let's go to the mosque³⁷*

Since religion has become the main factor determining political power and social identity, this however forced Awolowo to enlist the supports of the Muslims.

An attempt at another political dispensation of the Second Republic led to the lifting of ban on party politics in 1978 in preparation of military handing over to the civilian government for the conduct of the general election of 1979. It is however expedient to note that the parties formed were also along ethnic and religious lines; within this period political parties began to emerge in preparation for the elections. The parties that evolved were revitalization of the old political horse. Alamu corroborating this fact, posits that:

While in 1970's the likes of Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN) replaced formed Action Group, the National Party of Nigeria (NPN) and Nigeria Peoples Party of Nigeria (NPP) replaced formed Northern Peoples Congress (NPC), while Peoples Redemptive Party (PRP) share some tides with the North and Middle bath.³⁸

It is to be noted that since the new parties formed were a revitalization of the old political order, all of it were formed along religious lines, it had the hand of Esau and the voice of Jacob. Although they made claim to the fact that the party formed had national outlook while in the real sense, it did not.

Consequent upon the military takeover of power from the third abortive political dispensation and the counter-coup experience within the military parlance, the military regime of President Ibrahim Babangida in its drive to establish a new political order disbanded all political activities and established two political parties of his choice for Nigeria, a little to the left was Social Democratic Party (SDP) and a little to the right was National Republican Convention (NRC).³⁹ Supporting this view Kukah asserts that the illegitimate military Government of Babangida found solace in religion and its subsequent manipulations of passions which has kept religion in the front burner.⁴⁰ Mathew Kukah further enumerated that: "A two party arrangement almost automatically dislodged regionalism and ethnicity as metaphor for political expressions at the national level. Enter religion, given its potential and attraction as cross cutting cleavage, it became a major factor in political discourse."⁴¹ From the above observation it can be said that religion took the front burner in the political discourse because religion served as political identity.

In retrospect, with the appointment of General Abdulsalam Abubakar after the death of General Sanni Abacha on June 8, 1998, he inaugurated the independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in August 1998? These were Alliance for Democracy (AD), All Nigerian Peoples Party (ANPP) and Peoples Democratic Party and other parties.⁴² Yet, these parties still carried element of ethno-religious factors. The parties in question were also founded with religious undertones.

The Implication of the Intersection of Religion with Politics in Nigeria

The implication of the intersection of religion with politics is that, it serves as a source of conflict. Undoubtedly, the intersection of religion with politics in Nigeria has caused the nation great havoc and source of disagreement within the nation states and it has threatened the foundation of Nigeria as a nation. It is imperative to note the words of Obaro Ikime, as cited by Danmole, that:

Religion has been a significant phenomenon in the lives of Nigerians.... Religion and the state were inextricably linked together in... Nigeria. To a very large extent, religion serve as an integrating mechanism because it influence on the world view of the people that share common religion, while at the same time, it is a source of potential conflict with those whose belief system are not the same.⁴³

The above indicates that since religion and the state were inextricably linked hold that religion has led to an unpalatable situation where those who share the same views serves as an integrating mechanism and rallying point of getting things done because it work on the psyche of the people who shares the same faith to vote for their own candidate and at the same time it can be the cause of possible disagreement with those of other faiths. This has been a thin line of the problems encountered in our nascent democracy.

Another implication of the intersection of religion with politics is that it has led to extermination of good governance. It brought into being mediocre as leaders. This average or below average leaders have denied us probable leaders who could deliver the job and provide good governance. The high hopes and expectations that followed political independence became dashed as result of mediocre put in place as leaders. The reason for this has been enumerated by Nwosu when he notes that “the dearth of visionary, selfless, morally upright, altruistic political leaders have led to extermination of good governance.⁴⁴ The art of choosing mediocre as leaders has denied us competent, visionary, selfless, morally upright altruistic political leaders just because of religion, incompetent leaders are brought forth. Alamu in his treatise also corroborates the above saying bemoaning the idea of religion as a yardstick for electing our leaders, he asserts thus:

In as much as we continue bringing in religion.... into Nigerian politics we will continue to have mediocre as national leaders. This implies that as long as we continue to allow religion.... to become the nation’s trade mark, and spring board, no competent, capable, intelligent and rational political candidates would matche the country to the promise land.⁴⁵

He buttresses this further when he notes that the enthronement of religion and ethnicity in the Nigerian political system since independence to date has been worrisome and problematic. It has allowed miscreants, non-chalant, dullard and unpopular candidates to emerge as leaders.⁴⁶ In view of the above saying, one could not imagine Alhaji Sheu Shagari becoming a leader where competent hands such as Chief Obafemi Awolowo and Nnamdi Azikiwe among others, even the regime of General Muhammad Buhari can better be imagined to what is obtainable in the country as the country is tending towards retrogression.

Again, another implication of the intersection of religion in Nigeria politics is utilization of ethnicity as bait for voting. Nigeria is a country of many ethnic groups. Ethnicity in Nigeria, as Nwosu observes, involves a conscious and un-conscious acceptance of worldviews, values and ethics expressed along tribal lines. In other words, ethnicity refers to the identification of a group based on a perceived cultural distinctiveness that makes the group unto a people. This distinctiveness is believed to be expressed in language, music, values, arts, styles, literature, family life religion, ritual, food, naming, public life and material culture.⁴⁶

There is no doubt about the fact that ethnicity and religion have plunged Nigeria into bedlam of problems and challenges which have had dire consequences on the country. Ethnicity no doubts has been used as a yardstick for voting. Voting can be seen as expression of opinion in choosing between two or more people, so voting in an election has always been based on jostling for a particular position among the ethnic groups. It is to be noted that voting in Nigeria has been based on ethnicity which has always been causing conflicts and crises in every society which are usually products of conflicting interests for position which would generate either more rewards or political – powers – of these crises are often aided by interested parties, be they individual or groups or

government.⁴⁷ It is relevant to note that ethnicity has been used as a bait for voting, as Danmole perspicaciously opines that: “Islam and Christianity had become leading religions in Nigeria... However, these religions were to considerable extent regionally based, Islam in most of the North, Christianity in the southeast and mixture of Muslims and Christians in the South.”⁴⁸

With the north being predominantly Muslims, the east being Christians and Southwest mixture of Muslims and Christians they therefore vote along these religious line and this is often attributed to the fear of marginalization. In view of this, Alemazung Innocuously argues that: “These ethnic nationalities were forcefully unified for economic advantage... thereby leading to engendered dimension of pluralism, complexity and corporation. This form of unification produced an in built phobic competition and struggle for power domination and exploitation among the nationalities.”⁴⁹ From the above point of view, it has shown that each ethnic group has struggled to remain relevant in that it has produced inbuilt phobic competition and struggle for power, domination and exploitation among the citizens. This has further led to the next point of polarization and camps within the nation state.

The intersection of religion with politics in the nation has further led to polarization and division into camps within the nation states. Matthew Kukah in his view about how religion has polarized the nation and led the nations into camps asserts that: “The endless debates about democracy in Nigeria have largely been an unproductive exercise. Emotions, passions, prejudices ignorance and parochialism have often replaced reason... those debates have therefore ended up reinforcing, these prejudices and driving Nigerians to their various ethnic, religious and regional leaders where siege mentalities blossom.”⁵⁰

With the above sentiment one would have seen that emotions, prejudices, ignorance and parochialism have always replaced reasons and this has further polarized the nation and further divided them into camps.⁵¹ Matthew Kukah again quickly points to the fact that when the military began to toy with religion and ethnicity as means of legitimizing their power, these arose the purported joining of organization of Islamic conference.⁵² He went on to state that in 1986 the heat, acrimony and bitterness generated has led to eruption of violence in cataclysmic proportions in many states in northern Nigeria. He concludes that the polarization found full expression when the country was finally pitched as a battle ground between Christians and Muslim⁵³ Ottoh and Akintola sum this up when they offer their verdict to on religions influences on voting and campaigning has led to the polarization of the country. They posit that:

Religion is in advertently a major factor considered by electorates in their choice of candidates in an election or political leadership. Christian south would want to vote for the candidate from the region while the Muslim North will prefer a Muslim candidate. They inturn note that religion has become an instrument for the polarization of the country instead of unifying the country.⁵⁴

From the foregoing, it has been revealed that the intersection of religion with politics in Nigeria has further polarized and divided the nation to camps. An instance was when Muhamad Buhari failed to win an election in 2021 where hell was let loose, many souls were lost with properties worth millions destroyed.

Conclusion

This paper, no doubt, has examined the intersection of religion with politics in Nigeria. The paper observed that religion has always been the determining factor and social identity for politicians to win elections. The paper argued that right from the inception of partisan politics in Nigeria, religion is as old as party politics in Nigeria. In fact, the paper noted that politicians have always ridden on religion to consolidate their powers. This paper also observed that religion has become a potent force in the nation’s politics, given its manifestation in all political programmes, such as the inculcation of Sharia penal code in the constitution, establishment of pilgrims welfare for both Moslems and Christians, sponsoring the building of worship centres, observing prayers in governmental programmes, using religious sentiment for campaigns and elections, etc. All of these are indications that religion has been a tool for political identity in the nation. To this end, the paper concludes that religion has had great influence on Nigeria politics and the implication are that, it has led source of conflict, to extermination of good

governance, using religion and ethnicity as bait for voting, and has further polarized the nation into camps among others. This paper recommends that it is high time we dissected and separate religion from politics. Also, autonomous constitution should be given where secularity, in the true sense of it, should be promoted.

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